

Contribution to the Inventory of "Protected Animals" Sold As Bush Meats in Some Markets of Nord Ubangi Province, Democratic Republic Of The Congo

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ABSTRACT

The Province of "Nord Ubangi" is a forest ecosystem rich in biological resources among which one indicates the presence of the animals completely and/or partially protected by the law N0 82-002 of 28 May 1982 bearing regulation of hunting in Democratic Republic of the Congo. However, these biological resources are overexploited because of uncontrolled hunting and the poaching. The aim of this study was to survey the animals partially and/or completely protected in DRC, sold on various markets of the principal cities of Nord Ubangi Province in the form of bush meats or known by the bordering population. A questionnaire was prepared and used including the names of the animals and their localizations.

The present study identified 23 animal species partially protected (including 16 mammals, 05 birds and 02 reptiles) and 18 taxa completely protected (including 11 mammals, 05 birds and 02 reptiles). These results demonstrate the need for creating a protected area in order to safeguard this biodiversity. The development of a strategy for natural resources management through the Community based conservation would constitute for this purpose a better approach to prevent the land and conflicts, and thus to ensure an equitable sharing of benefits between the local communities. Thus, the creation of a priority protected area in Nord Ubangi according to this approach would make it possible to generate employment for the local population in accordance with the Access and benefits sharing and Bio-prospection of the Convention on biological diversity. For that, it is thus desirable that a participative cartography study with the local communities could be carried out in order to delimit the zones to be protected.

Key words: Biodiversity, ethno-zoological survey, Nord Ubangi province, Priority protected area, Nagoya protocol

INTRODUCTION

The Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) is a vast territory of almost 2350000km², located in the humid tropics, on both sides of the equator, with an enormous economic potential in natural resources. Its horse stance to the Equator gives it a wide latitudinal zonation resulting in a diversity of natural ecosystems (15 eco-regions) associated to high levels to the biodiversity [1, 2]. From the perspective of species, the country is full of rare specimens, some of which are found now here else in the world. This is particularly the case of *Okapia johnstoni* (Ndumba in Ngbandi language), a fully protected animal that is found in the Nord Ubangi [3].

However, although the loss of biological resources is a natural phenomenon, man accelerated the extinction rate drastically. In tropical regions, particularly in DRC, the lack of these resources can be a very serious threat to the survival of populations of forest areas. This is namely the case of excessive abstraction that cannot allow the animal stock to recover and is

an important indication of the level of pressure on the wildlife by the local population.

For this purpose, conscious of the danger of the biological diversity loss in the world due to the uncontrolled exploitation of natural resources, the International Community initiated the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) of which the relevance was recognized and approved by more than 150 states at the Earth Summit, held in June 1992 in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. Thus, the conservation of the biological diversity, the sustainable use of these resources and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from their use would ensure a safer future for the forthcoming generations [4, 5].

The Province of Nord Ubangi (NU) has an area of 56632.5 km², most of which consists of the rainforest [6]. This forest ecosystem is ecologically threatened by human activities and could lead to the resources depletion and the increase of poverty.

To avoid/prevent such an ecological disaster and/or social, it is important and urgent to assess the biodiversity that abounds the province of NU in order to help and propose strategies for a sustainable development through *in* and/or *ex situ* biodiversity conservation. To our best knowledge, no research has been published on the biological resources of the Province of NU at part from our work [3, 7, 8].

Nevertheless, the knowledge of these resources is of an evident interest. Indeed, the results of this survey can be exploited in the process of drafting of the development plan of the new areas to be protected in the NU for the implementation of sustainable participatory management systems of the biological resources of this province.

The present survey aimed to inventory the animals partially and/or fully protected by the Congolese Law no. 82-002 of 28 May 1982 indicating the regulation of hunting in Democratic Republic of the Congo, in view of their conservation and of the implementation of applied research protocol according to the recommendations of the CBD.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Overview Nord Ubangi district

NU is a province in Democratic Republic of the Congo. Several people are living there and speaking different languages. However, the dominant peoples are Ngbandi-Sango. Besides these, there are also other peoples, such as the Mono, the Gbaya, the Furu, the Gbagiro, the Gbanziri, the Kpala, the Mbanza and the Ngbaka [6].

RESULTS

The animal partially protected by the law in the tropical rainforest of Nord Ubangi and their geographical location is listed in table 1.

Table 1: Location of partially protected animals in the Province of Nord Ubangi, Democratic Republic of the Congo

Animals	Scientific names (FrenhNames/Vernacular Names)	Location
Primates	<i>Cercopithecus mitis</i> (Singe argenté ou bleu/Ngambo)	Businga
	<i>Cercopithecus kandti</i> (Singe doré/kala)	Abuzi
	<i>Colobus spp</i> (Colobes/Funga)	Kota-Koli, Businga, Wapinda et Abuzi
Carnivores	<i>Felis serval</i> (Serval/N'dumba)	Wapinda
	<i>Panthera pardus</i> (Léopard/Zê)	Gbadolite, Abuzi
	<i>Panthera leo</i> (Lion/Mbata)	Wapinda, Kota-Koli
Artiodactyla	<i>Syncerus caffernanus</i> (Buffle nain/Ngba)	Abuzi, Liongo, Sokoro et Bosobolo
	<i>Tragelaphus scriptus</i> (Antilope harnachée/Ba)	Nord Ubangi
	<i>Tragelaphu seurycerus</i> (Antilope bongo/Vonga)	Bosobolo
	<i>Cephalopus sylvicultor</i> (Antilope de bois/Vonga)	Kota-Koli, Abuzi, Gbadolite
	<i>Onotragus lechwe</i> (Cobe de marais/Mbengele)	Abuzi, Businga, Kota-Koli et Bosobolo

Figure 1: Geographical location of Nord Ubangi
Ethno-zoological survey and identification of animal species

We interviewed, based on their consent, hunters and sellers of bush meat in major cities of the Nord Ubangi province (Abumombazi/Abuzi, Wapinda, Yakoma, Kota-Koli, Mobayi-Mbongo, Gbadolite, Businga, Bosobolo). The investigation covered the period from January to December 2013. Its aim was to identify animals "partially and /or completely protected" from the rainforest of Nord Ubangi sold as bush meat. The information collected was related primarily with animal names and locations. All the animals were identified thanks to the identification keys supplemented by information obtained from various works of literature [9, 10]. In total, 100 people were surveyed. The level of knowledge of wild animals has been used as a criterion of respondent selection

	<i>Tragelaphus spekei</i> (Sitatunga/Bita)	Abuzi
	<i>Potamochoerus porcus</i> (Potamochère/Mbenge)	Abuzi
	<i>Phacochoerus aethiopicus</i> (Phacochère/Nzeli)	Nord Ubangi
	<i>Hippopotamus amphibius</i> (Hippopotame/Mbimba)	Abuzi, Businga, Yakoma, Mobayi
Reptiles	<i>Crocodylus niloticus</i> (Crocodyle du Nil/Ngunde)	Yakoma
Pholidotes	<i>Osteolaemus tetraspis</i> (Crocodyle à nuque cuirassée/Ngunde)	Yakoma
	<i>Manis temincki</i> (Pangolin terrestre/Kakolo ou Kă)	Nord Ubangi
Birds	<i>Ciccaba woodfordii</i> (Hiboux et Chouettes/Sukulu)	Nord Ubangi
	<i>Caprimulgus batesi</i> (Engoulevents/Ngwa)	Nord Ubangi
	<i>Apus spp.</i> (Martinets/Gole ou Polo)	Nord Ubangi
	<i>Casmerodius albus</i> (Aigrette/Gua ou Koloke)	Nord Ubangi
	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i> (Garde-bœuf/ Nyange)	Nord Ubangi

The list of animals fully protected by law in the tropical rainforest of Nord Ubangi and their geographical location is given in Table 2.

Table 2: Location of animals fully protected in the Province of Nord Ubangi, Democratic Republic of the Congo

Animals	Scientific names (French Names/vernacular names)	Location
Primates	<i>Pan troglodytes</i> (Chimpanzé/Nvo)	Abuzi, Bosobolo, Bokunda
	<i>Colobus congolensis</i> (Colobe/Funga)	Abuzi
	<i>Cercopithecus ascanius</i> (- /Mbida)	Abuzi, Businga
Proboscidés	<i>Loxodonta africana africana</i> (Eléphant de savane/Doli)	Monzo à Bosobolo, Abuzi
	<i>Loxodonta africana cyclotis</i> (Eléphant de forêt/Doli)	Yakoma, Businga, Abuzi
	<i>Loxodonta Africana pumilio</i> (Eléphant nain/Doli)	Yakoma, Businga, Abuzi
Artiodactyles	<i>Giraffa camelopardalis</i> (Girafe/Gbodi ou Bita)	Abuzi, Wapinda, Pandu à Bosobolo
	<i>Okapia johnstoni</i> (Okapi/Ndumba)	Abuzi, Maniko
Carnivores	<i>Felis aurata</i> (Chat doré/Kangbwa)	Nord Ubangi
	<i>Osbornictis piscivora</i> (Civette aquatique/Ganvana)	Nord Ubangi
Pholidotes	<i>Manis gigantea</i> (Pangolin géant/Kabondo)	Abuzi, Wapinda
Reptiles	<i>Crocodylu scataphractus</i> (Crocodyle à museau étroit ou Faux gavial/Ngunde)	Abuzi, Yakoma
	<i>Kinixys erosa</i> (Tortue terrestre/Nako)	Yakoma, Bosobolo
Oiseaux	<i>Afropavo congoensis</i>	Nord Ubangi

	(Paon congolais/Kulungu)	
	<i>Sagittaris serpentarices</i> (Messager serpenteaire/Bondo ou Menengele)	Nord Ubangi
	<i>Balearita pavenina</i> (Grue couronnée/Ngabe)	Nord Ubangi
	<i>Psittacus erithacus</i> (Perroquet gris ou jacot/Kukulu) <i>Poicephalus gulielmi</i> (Perroquet vert calotte rouge)	Bosobolo, Businga, Abuzi

It is clear from this preliminary investigation that the NU is an area rich in biodiversity. Indeed, we can find 23 partially protected animal species (including 16 mammals, 05 birds and 02 reptiles) and 18 strictly protected taxa (including 11 mammals, 05 birds and 02 reptiles). This result shows that the forest of NU is an ecosystem which can be used to create a priority protected area in order to conserve these genetic resources, common inheritance of mankind. In addition, it should also be noticed that besides the above mentioned protected species, the NU is full of other unprotected taxa with high medicinal and/or economic value as *Python regius*: Nkwa (Ngbandi), *Chamaeleo chamaeleo*: kulangaye (Ngbandi), Giant African Threadfin (*Polydactylus quadrifilis*): capitaine (French).

The following figure shows the photo of *Cercopithecus ascanius* captured from the field (Selling point: Abumombazi).

Figure 2: *Cercopithecus Ascanius*

DISCUSSION

In Africa, hunting ensures a large share of food supply to rural populations [11]. However, the population growth is responsible for the constant increase in demand for games and

other iconic or emblematic animals such as chimpanzees and elephants. This situation is particularly dramatic in the forest of Nord Ubangi, a 'hot spot' of the biodiversity as stated by the list of protected species which are present. Studies on the state of the biodiversity in the forests of Central Africa show the reduction or the collapse of large mammal populations due to poaching in order for the trade of bush meat and their habitat destruction. However, given that the rate of reproduction of these large mammals is very slow, so this practice makes their populations highly vulnerable to all shooting modes [12, 13]. As matter of fact, the concern to protect the natural ecological inheritance brought DRC to ratify several international agreements in order to convert 17% of its national territory as protected areas [14].

According to the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora threatened with extinction (CITES, 1979) [15], nature has a right to existence and intrinsic value, implying a must of being protected against human actions. For this purpose, the protection of species and ecosystems that host them becomes a sacred duty because to the concept of "biodiversity" is added the "cultural diversity". Then, biodiversity is presented as an inheritance on which indigenous and local populations have some rights [16].

To prevent conflicts between the State which is the manager of the biodiversity and local people, the CBD (1992) established a legal framework for biological resources operating terms for fair and equitable sharing of benefits taking into account all rights over those resources [15, 17-19]. This notion of fair and equitable sharing is fundamental in the context of the current study. In fact, the knowledge of animals fully or partially protected by law would initiate projects for their conservation *in* and/or *ex situ* in order to maintain the biodiversity through the creation of protected areas. These protected areas include national parks, natural reserves, botanical gardens, and so on [20].

To date, the NU Province has no officially recognized protected areas. Research on protected animals would better monitor and prevent the extinction of these animals. In order to guarantee the rights of the local population on these genetic resources, the results of this study would initiate the process of creating protected areas through sharing agreement to mutually terms agreed between the local communities and Congolese estate according to the principles presented in the Nagoya Protocol [15, 18, 19].

NU biodiversity is currently facing a series of very serious threats of which the uncontrolled hunting, slash and burn cultivation (deforestation) and poaching. In order to ensure sustainable exploitation of biological resources, it is important to think today about the protection of the NU forest ecosystems.

Indeed, the implementation of the CBD in terms of protected animals in the NU province is a very interesting approach for the *ex situ* and/or *in situ* conservation (protected areas) would allow a fair and equitable sharing of benefits from the rights of visits and entrance fees, in terms of financial compensations or royalties by paying annually to the local community benefits for finance/support of development projects with visible social impact [20, 21].

The NU province is a little known site in need of protection. In fact, besides its ecological, cultural and scientific value, the biodiversity plays an important role in the District's economy by providing the raw materials needed for human survival (food, medicines, fiber, construction, energy materials). Therefore, this province has an exceptional biodiversity potential to be conserved enhanced and developed on ecological sustainable basis. However, this forest cannot be managed at the expense of the people who live in, or in the absence of active participation [22]. In addition, if a priority protected area should be created in the NU province, then it should be compulsory to teach the local population how to use new agricultural technologies with reduced environmental impact as well as the breeding and domestication of wild animals in order to serve as sources of animal proteins for the population in order to limit its pressure on the forest.

CONCLUSION

Nord Ubangi is a rich forest ecosystem in biological resources amongst we denote the presence of animals fully and/or partially protected by the law No.82-002of 28 May 1982 on the regulation of hunting in Democratic Republic of the Congo. However, these biological resources are overexploited because of uncontrolled hunting and poaching. Henceforth, the need to create a protected area is important in order to conserve these animals sustainably. Currently, the nature conservation is yet a bet that can only succeed through the effective participation of all components in the daily management of natural resources. The conservation of biodiversity without human intervention except research, inherited from colonization, has reached its limits and cannot guarantee better management of these natural resources.

The implementation of natural resource management strategy through the community conservation may for this purpose be a better way to prevent customary as well property conflicts, and thus ensure a fair sharing of benefits among local communities. Creating a priority protected area in the Nord Ubangi province; according to this approach would generate jobs for the local population in accordance with the implementation of the Access and Benefit Sharing advantages and Bio-prospecting of the CBD. Thus, it is desirable to achieve a participatory mapping with local communities in order to demarcate areas to be protected and estimate the indices of abundance and the density of emblematic species in this humid forest ecosystem. It would also be desirable for bush meat biomass marketed in major markets to be measured.

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ANNEX: Some selected animals (source: <http://www.googleimages.org/>)

Annex 1: *Okapia johnstoni*

[1] Annex 2: *Cercopithecus mitis*

[2] Annex 3: *Cercopithecus kandti*

[3] Annex 4: *Felis serval*

Annex 5: *Panthera pardus*

[4]

Annex 6: *Crocodylus niloticus*

[5]

Annex 7: *Osteolaemus tetraspis*

Annex 8: *Manis temincki*

[6]

Annex 9: *Syncerus caffer nanus*

Annex 10: *Tragelaphus scriptus*

[7]

Annex 11: *Tragelaphus eurycerus*

[8] Annex 12: *Onotragus lechwe*

Annex 13: *Tragelaphus spekei*

[9]

Annex 14: *Potamochoerus porcus*

[10]

[11] Annex 15: *Phacochoerus aethiopicus*

Annex 16: *Hippopotamus amphibius*

[12]

Annex 17: *Manis gigantea*

[13]

[14] Annex 18: *Afropavo congoensis*

[15] Annex 19: *Psittacus erithacus*

Annex 20: *Felis aurata*

[16]

[17] Annex 21: *Pan troglodytes*

[21]

[18] Annex 22: *Giraffa camelopardalis*

[19] Annex 23: *Loxodonta africana cyclotis*

[20] Annex 24: *Sagittaris serpentarices*